

The Decisions To Make (In An Advertising Agency)

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Abstract: *This case is about Mr. Pranay Bharadwaj who with his hard work rose to an entrepreneur and initiated Total Advertising after understanding the advertising trade. In the case author has made an effort to understand the need of customers in the changing times. At the time of this problem Mr. Pranay put emphasis on research parameters to use it as a tool of decision making thus leading to customer satisfaction.*

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INTRODUCTION

Total is in advertising business since last 21 years. It has a good client network and the company is run by Pranay Bharadwaj. It was started by him with his savings of Rs.1,00,000 and a borrowed loan of Rs.80,000 from his wife in 1992 in the city of Bombay which today is known as Mumbai. With years of dedication and hard work the organization today has earned itself a good repute in the market. The company does hire some talented staff every year and train them to fit in this competitive market and to serve its esteemed clients in the best of capacity. This is something which has made the organization survive and grow even in adverse conditions. The organization always believed in providing special attention to its clients need and thus has developed some long lasting bonds with its clientage.

Career of Pranay

Mr. Pranay Bharadwaj was a Management Graduate and got his first break in an advertising company when he moved to Mumbai with the goal of making a career in 1984. He started his first job on a salary of Rs. 5,000 per month which was a good salary to start at that time as a fresher. Pranay came from a small city of Alwar in Rajasthan and was not acquainted with lot of people in Bombay (Present day Mumbai). Thus he was giving majority of his time to the organization. He was not only involved with creative team at early days but was also working to make up new clients for the organization. With his hard work, determination and passion for his job, he soon was a popular name among his peers and management.

Pranay's Growth Pattern

Pranay, started his career accidentally when he met Mr. Rajesh Ranjan, a manager with an advertising agency since last few years. The friendly atmosphere of the agency along with his good relation with the then manager, Mr. Rajesh Ranjan prompted him to be the part of this team. And in no time he was part of Bull Advertising which cater to its clients, though confide to Mumbai. Pranay who joined as a trainee worked hard and understood every aspect of his work. He would initially spend almost 12-14 hours working in this organization. He soon was well versed with his job and started taking various initiatives which proved to be beneficial for the organization. He made trips to various parts of Maharashtra and made new clients in various cities like Nagpur, Aurangabad, Kolhapur, Nasik and Pune in particular. He soon within 6 years of his career had made his organization grow and thus agency too reciprocated by giving raise and promotions for his efforts. By the end of 1990 Pranay was the senior manager just next to Shri Rajesh Ranjan who was the general manager in the firm, which rose from the staff of 8 people in 1984 to staff of professional 32 people by the end of 1990.

An Opportunity

The sailing was good for Bull advertising and its business was growing too. In year 1991 which was the landmark year in the economy of India, when then finance minister Dr. Manmohan Singh came with liberalization

and thus changing the scenario of the market with many global players ready to enter the Indian market. Pranay looked at it as an opportunity and thought to start his own business.

Setting a firm

Pranay thought of starting his long cherished dream of his own enterprise. He knew that world was growing and new opportunities waits at every possible step now in this near era of development. So he decided that he will cater from the financial capital of India, Mumbai. Eventually on March 4,1992 on Wednesday, Pranay opened his office in Mumbai .

Satellite television era

After the liberalization various sectors which were untouched or were in government dominance got opened for private players. One such untouched area was that of television where private players too came in the market. From two channels prior to 1991, Indian viewers were exposed to more than 50 channels by 1996. And soon after many private channels entered this unexplored market. With this advertising agency too started getting lot of business for advertisements on these private channels more rightly so, as they become part and parcel in the life of common man.

Changing times

The task today is demanding with Total advertising. The competition is cut throat and in industry where Total advertising survives, the way is providing best services to its clients to built loyal customers or clients or to provide full value for the money they have invested in advertising. Hence Total advertisings have some tasks to make some right decisions in the interest of its clients. There are various selections he has to make for his clients based on the data provided by the research organization of the top 5 rated programs as per their viewership. The given is provided in the Exhibit 1 which states a study conducted by the famous research organization to understand the viewers response on TV viewership conducted among 2,00,000 TV respondents. While, Exhibit 2 provides a little insight to these listed TV program which covers almost 80% of the popularity of TV viewers. On the basis of the given Total advertising has to provide suitable programs for the given below advertisers so that he can trap this market and make them his loyal customers.

Times Ahead

There are several solutions which Total advertising has to find to cater to the requirement of its clients, some such questions are as follows, state what will be their decisions in the interest of their clients, Try to base your answers on the basis of the survey by the research organization and general understanding about Target Market.

1. From the given details among the top 5 programs, which you think is the most popular program on the basis of the survey.
2. Which of the given program shall be charging highest price for their 20 second advertising slot?
3. Which of the given program shall be charging least price for their 20 second advertising slot?
4. One of their clients need to introduce a new Denim Brand targeting towards the youth in the range of particularly 17-22 years in the market, which of the TV program platform shall be an ideal platform for their product understanding their market segment.

5. Another client which is a well established Saree store having its branches across India is about to start a 10% to 20% sales on its products. They wish to start it at the same time across India and want to facilitate it all stores. Help the Saree Store to choose an ideal channel or program to target its market.
6. The New car by famous Brand across the globe has entered in Indian market, which TV platform best suited for their promotional activity.
7. As we know the Cola have always been on advertising war with each other. Of the given which activity of program they will prefer for their advertising or if they have a choice to sponsor a program.
8. An advertisement of Shampoo which offers free soap, what according shall be the right program for them for advertising.
9. A Surrogated Advertising of famous beverages will hit the TV screen at which program prime time.
10. Which channel shall be best suited for the advertisement of the popular product ‘TEA’.
11. The famous book publishers, Bookson want to advertise, which program will be suggested to enhance their cost on advertising.
12. Will a Tea advertisement be suitable for a channel in Tamil or on Hindi Channel?

What were the advertising decisions taken by Total Advertising in the best interest of its clients? Support your answers with a reason.

EXHIBIT 1

TV PROGRAM	RATINGS				
	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>3</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>5</u>
JBC	18	27	13	10	12
T-20 Match	20	13	16	18	13
Kal Tak News	17	21	17	17	8
TV Roadies	12	9	17	18	24
Saas Bahu Serial	13	10	17	17	23

(The given values are in percentage and give preference of viewers of top five most watched TV program)

EXHIBIT 2

1. JBC: It’s a popular game show which is telecasted at the prime peak time of 9pm to 10 pm. The given program provides an opportunity to participants to earn huge sum of money by answering right answer from the options given.
2. T-20 match: This is the format of cricket which has become extremely popular in no time in this cricket crazy country. It is cricket match of 20 over’s for each team making it a fast track cricket in this era of fast food.
3. Kal Tak News: This is the most popular news channel. The given channel is a Hindi news channel and is extremely popular news channel in the hindi language segment.

4. TV Roadies: A program which is popular as the program for Generation Next. The program has grown its popularity among the college students.
5. Saas-Bahu Serial: A Soap which has got attention of all women and is based on social and family values of people.

(Please note all programs are on air at the time of making these advertisement decisions for their clients)